

AN IMPERFECT PRODUCTION AND TRADE CREDIT INVENTORY MODEL WITH TIME VARYING DEMAND, REPAIR AND CONSTANT PRODUCTION RATES UNDER INFLATIONARY CONDITIONS

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

This paper formulated the impact of an inventory model for imperfect manufacturing process. Demand rate and repair rate are exponentially function of time. Production rate is constant and collection rate are depending on demand. Due to the demand, they are also function of time. Model is developed to minimize the total inventory cost by considering only one type of raw material and by using permissible delay in payments under inflationary environment. Numerical example are used to find the analytical result. Sensitivity analysis is used to fulfil the effect of distinct parameter on the optimal policy.

1. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW:

In today's time, it is saw that a customer is permitted some period before setting the account with the supplier or the producer. The customer does not have to pay any interest during the fixed period but if the payments delay, the supplier will charge the interest for the period. Permissible delay on payments is a consistent factor of market and constitutes a major source of short term financing. Trade credit is more useful for transaction. The wide range of researchers work on it. Firstly, Haley and Higgins (1973) gave an inventory model on trade credit. The purpose of this model calculates the jointly order quantity and optimal payment time. Singh et al. (2011) worked on inventory model for deteriorating objects under the condition permissible delay in payments.

A repairable inventory system has two type inventory which are inventory of goods ready-for-issue and the inventory of shell available for repair. Firstly Repair-inventory system was given by Schrady

(1967). He derived an Economic order quantity inventory model for repairable items. There were no direct disposal cost for the production and recovery (repair) rates. Nahmias and Rivera (1979) extended Schrady's inventory model for repair rate. There also derived some formulas for optimal repair. Richter (1996) introduced about the EOQ model for repair and disposal model. Richter (1997) extended the paper of Richter. Dobos and Richter (2003) gave a manufacturing/reutilizing model with stationary demands and return rates. They derived two model for minimize the cost and to generalize the first model. Dobos and Richter (2004) extended their previous work by assuming various repair and manufacturing group in a time interval. Also, Dobos and Richter (2006) drawn-out their previous work by assuming the quality of refunded products. El-Saadany and Jaber (2010) increased Dobos and Richter works by assuming that the refund rate of used items is depend on a demand function. Demand is dependent on the approval quality degree and getting price of refunded items. Inderfurth et al. (2005) gave a model for lot sizing in a production system with rework and product deterioration. EPQ model derived to optimize the cost and lot size. Konstantaras and Papachristos (2008) introduced about an optimal policy and carrying cost stability regions in periodic review inventory with manufacturing and remanufacturing options. Some of the other research papers related to repair inventory system were given by Jaber and Saadany (2011), Jaber and Rosen (2008), Konstantaras and Skouri (2010), Konstantaras et al. (2010). Remanufacturing is the procedure that compile and remanufactures used objects to attain quality standards that are "as-good-as those of new products". The concept of reuse of the product is operated and defined in many different forms depending on the perspective. Kokkinaki et al. (2001) discussed a closed-loop supply chain model considering on reuse of the products. Reverse logistic operations can lead to a noteworthy increment in profits. Some of the papers linked to reused of the products was discovered by Rogers and Tibben-Lembke (1998). Chung and Wee (2008) gave an inventory model for worsening items. In this paper the flow of refunded items are depending on both the price and quality of items. Chung and Wee (2011) increased their work for short life –cycle deteriorating product remanufacturing in a green supply chain inventory control system. Alamri (2011) gave an integrated manufacturing model for new items and remanufacturing of refunded items which used to optimize the total cost. Hsueh (2011) discovered inventory control policies in a manufacturing/remanufacturing system with demand rate and return rate of products for normal distribution. Singh and Saxena (2013) produced a model for closed loop supply chain system with flexible manufacturing and reverse logistic operation under shortage for deteriorating objects. Sarkar and Moon (2014) gave a model for an imperfect production process and used to find the optimal solutions for lead time demand. Sarkar et al. (2014) investigated the economic production quantity (EPQ) inventory model for a single stage manufacturing of finished items. Many researcher work on imperfect items to reduces the complete manufacturing-inventory costs. Some of the researcher are C'ardenasBarr'on et al. (2016) derived easy and derivation to joint determination of the replenishment lot size. Kim and Sarkar (2017) discussed about multi-stage clear production process with quality

improvement and lead time based on set up cost for imperfect objects. Sarkar and Saren (2016) proposed a model for product inspection policy for imperfect production system with inspection errors and warranty cost. Taleizadeh et al. (2013) gave an inventory model for multiproduct under fuzzy random sale and backordered quantities. The main focus of this model to determine the maximum level of inventory with the help of mathematical model. Tayyab and Sarkar (2000). Sarkar and Mahapatra (2015), Taleizadeh et al. (2011), and Taleizadeh et al. (2009) gave a fuzzy inventory model by assuming different situations. Benkherouf and Omar (2017) analyzed a model time varying demand rate. Jain et al. (2018) gave an inventory model for imperfect manufacturing process with time varying demand. Omar and Yeo (2009) discovered a manufacturing and repair inventory model with time-varying demand. In this model, there are various manufacturing runs, various ordering raw material lots, and various repair runs. This model used to find a joint policy for raw materials and repair product. Omar and Yeo (2012) presented an inventory model for a manufacturing system which covers a continuous time changing demand within a finite planning horizon. The objective of this model, determine jointly the duration of production run, repair run, and cycle time such that the total cost of the inventory system is minimized. It is assumed that demand and repair rate are varying with time. Permissible delay on payments for imperfect and used items and inflation are also used. This paper is organized as in the section 2 assumption, section 3 notation, section 4 existing mathematical model, section 5 numerical example, sensitivity analysis and observation, section 6 exit conclusion, section 7 references.

2. ASSUMPTIONS

- i. A single type of manufacturing inventory system is assumed over the planning horizon.
- ii. The demand rate $D(t)$ is an exponentially function of time such that $D(t) = ae^{bt}$ where a, b are constants and $a > b$.
- iii. Production rate is constant at any time
- iv. The repair rate $R(t)$ is an exponentially function of time t such that $R(t) = c ae^{dt}$ and $R(t) > D(t)$ for all t ; where c, d are constants.
- v. The collection rate of the used items from customers, $C(t)$, is proportional to the demand rate; it is determined with the following expression: $C(t) = \phi D(t)$, $0 \leq \phi \leq 1$.
- vi. Permissible delay (trade credit) on payment for imperfect objects is used with purchasing cost c_3 .
- vii. All fake and remanufactured items are reviewed and after the screening process are classify as good or imperfect items.
- viii. Only one type of raw material is used to manufacture the final product.
- ix. Inflation is also used in this model.
- x. Shortages are not allowed.

3. NOTATION:

C_1 – Ordering cost of raw material

C_P – Ordering cost of manufacture run

C_R – Ordering cost of repair run

h_p – Holding cost of final items

h_R – Holding cost of used and imperfect items

h_1 – Holding cost of raw material

c_2 – Production cost

c_3 – Purchasing cost of imperfect and used items

E – Interest which can be earned for imperfect and used items

R – Interest charge which invested for imperfect and used items

M – Permissible delay in payments

U_R – Returned used item cost

l – Inspection cost, i – remanufacturing cost

k – Production coefficient, ϕ – Collection rate, r – Inflation rate, θ – Rate of imperfect production and repair runs, q_1 – Quantity of raw materials

$I_{ui}(t)$ – Inventory level of used and imperfect items at any time t

$I_f(t)$ – Inventory level of finished items at any time t

$I_R(t)$ – Inventory level of remanufacturing items at any time t

$I_r(t)$ – Inventory level of raw materials at any time t

$IP(t)$ – Interest payable at any time

$IE_i(t)$ – Interest earned at any time

4. MATHEMATICAL FORMATION MODEL

Production run is within of the interval $[0, t_1]$, during this time the inventory level of raw material 1 decreases. The demand $D(t)$ occurs during the period $[0, T]$. In the interval $[0, t_2]$ the inventory level of

imperfect items and collected used items are being accumulated. As a result, the repair process of these items starts at t_2 and finishes at t_3 . Notice that collection of used items occurs always from 0 to t_3 . The imperfect items are generated during the intervals $[0, t_1]$ and $[t_1, t_3]$. During the repair run there is not required raw material 1 because the used and imperfect items are remanufactured on themselves. It is easy to see in Figure that the duration of production run is t_1 repair run is $t_3 - t_2$, production cycle t_2 , repair cycle $T - t_2$, used and imperfect items cycle is t_3 , raw material 1 cycle is t_1 , and cycle time is T .

Figure :inventory level

MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR PRODUCTION AND REPAIR RATE

From the given figure the differential equation

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{u_i}'(t) &= \phi D(t) + \theta P(t) & 0 \leq t \leq t_1 & \dots\dots\dots eq(1) \\
 I_{u_i}'(t) &= \phi D(t) & t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 & \dots\dots\dots eq(2) \\
 I_{u_i}'(t) &= \phi D(t) - (1 - \theta) R(t) & t_2 \leq t \leq t_3 & \dots\dots\dots eq(3) \\
 I_f'(t) &= (1 - \theta)P(t) - D(t) & 0 \leq t \leq t_1 & \dots\dots\dots eq(4) \\
 I_f'(t) &= -D(t) & t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 & \dots\dots\dots eq(5) \\
 I_R'(t) &= (1 - \theta)R(t) - D(t) & t_2 \leq t \leq t_3 & \dots\dots\dots eq(6) \\
 I_R'(t) &= -D(t) & t_3 \leq t \leq T & \dots\dots\dots eq(7) \\
 I_r'(t) &= -q_1 P & 0 \leq t \leq t_1 & \dots\dots\dots eq(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

with boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{u_i}(0) &= 0, I_{u_i}(t_3) = 0, I_f(0) = 0, I_f(t_2) = 0, I_R(T) = 0, \\
 I_R(t_2) &= 0, I_r(t_1) = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

where $D(t) = ae^{bt}$

$$P(t) = kD(t) = kae^{bt}, \quad P(t) > D(t)$$

$$C(t) = \psi D(t)$$

Taking equation (1)

$$I'_{u_i}(t) = \varphi D(t) + \theta P, \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1$$

$$I'_{u_i}(t) = \varphi a e^{bt} + \theta P, \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1$$

$$= \varphi a e^{bt} + \theta P$$

Integrating w.r.t. t

$$I_{u_i}(t) = \int_0^t (\varphi a e^{bt} + \theta P) dt$$

$$I_{u_i}(t) = \frac{\varphi a (e^{bt} - 1)}{b} + \theta Pt \quad eq(11)$$

Now taking equation(2)

$$I'_{u_i}(t) = \varphi D(t), \quad t_1 \leq t \leq t_2$$

$$= \varphi a e^{bt} - (1 - \theta) c e^{dt} \quad eq(12)$$

Integrating wrt. t

$$I_{u_i}(t) = \int_{t_1}^t (\varphi a e^{bt} - (1 - \theta) c e^{dt}) dt$$

$$I_{u_i}(t) = \frac{\varphi a (e^{bt} - e^{bt_1})}{b} - \frac{(1 - \theta) c (e^{dt} - e^{dt_1})}{d} \quad eq(13)$$

$I_{u_i}(t)$, subtract eq.(13) from eq.(11)

For contuing of

$$0 = \left\{ \frac{\varphi a (e^{bt} - e^{bt_1})}{b} - \frac{(1 - \theta) c (e^{dt} - e^{dt_1})}{d} \right\} - \left\{ \frac{\varphi a (e^{bt} - 1)}{b} + \theta Pt \right\}$$

At $t=t_2$

$$\frac{\varphi a (e^{bt_2} - 1)}{b} + \theta Pt_2$$

$$= \frac{\varphi a (e^{bt_2} - e^{bt_1})}{b} - \frac{(1 - \theta) c (e^{dt_2} - e^{dt_1})}{d} \quad eq(14)$$

Now taking equation (4)

$$I'_f(t) = (1 - \theta)P - D(t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1$$

$$I'_f(t) = (1 - \theta)P - a e^{bt}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1$$

Integrating w.r.t. t

$$I_f(t) = \int_0^t \{(1 - \theta)P - a e^{bt}\} dt$$

$$= (1 - \theta)Pt - \frac{a(e^{bt} - 1)}{b} \quad eq(15)$$

Now taking equation (5)

$$I'_f(t) = -D(t), \quad t_1 \leq t \leq t_2$$

$$= -a e^{bt}$$

Integrating wrt. t

$$I_{u_i}(t)$$

$$= - \int_{t_1}^t (a e^{bt}) dt$$

$$I_{u_i}(t) = \frac{-a(e^{bt} - e^{bt_1})}{b} \quad eq(16)$$

$I_f(t)$, subtract eq.(14) from eq.(15)

For contuing of

$$0 = \left\{ \frac{-a(e^{bt} - e^{bt_1})}{b} \right\}$$

$$- \left\{ (1 - \theta)Pt - \frac{a(e^{bt} - 1)}{b} \right\}$$

At $t=t_1$

$$(1 - \theta)Pt_1 - \frac{a(e^{bt_1}-1)}{b} = \frac{-a(e^{bt_1}-e^{bt_2})}{b}$$

$$t_1 = \frac{a(e^{bt_2}-1)}{bP(1-\theta)} \tag{17}$$

Now taking equation (6)

$$I'_R(t) = (1 - \theta)R(t) - D(t), \quad t_2 \leq t \leq t_3$$

$$I'_R(t) = (1 - \theta)ce^{dt} - ae^{bt}$$

Integrating wrt. t,

$$I_R(t) = \int_{t_2}^t \{(1 - \theta)ce^{dt} - ae^{bt}\} dt$$

$$= \frac{-a(e^{bt}-e^{bt_2})}{b} + \frac{(1-\theta)c(e^{dt}-e^{dt_2})}{d} \tag{18}$$

Now taking equation (7)

$$I'_R(t) = -D(t), \quad t_3 \leq t \leq T$$

$$= -ae^{bt}$$

Integrating wrt. t

$$I_R(t) = -\int_T^t (ae^{bt}) dt$$

$$I_R(t) = \frac{-a(e^{bt}-e^{bT})}{b} \tag{19}$$

$I_f(t)$, subtract eq.(14) from eq.(15)

For contuing of

$$0 = \left\{ \frac{-a(e^{bt}-e^{bT})}{b} \right\} - \left\{ \frac{-a(e^{bt}-e^{bt_2})}{b} + \frac{(1-\theta)c(e^{dt}-e^{dt_2})}{d} \right\}$$

At $t=t_3$

$$\frac{-a(e^{bt_3}-e^{bT})}{b} = \frac{-a(e^{bt_3}-e^{bt_2})}{b} + \frac{(1-\theta)c(e^{dt_3}-e^{dt_2})}{d} \tag{20}$$

from eq(14) and eq(20)

$$t_2 = \frac{1}{b} \ln \left| e^{bt} + [k(1-\theta)-1](e^{bt_1}-1) \right| \tag{21}$$

$$t_3 = \frac{1}{b} \ln \left| e^{bt_2} + \frac{ad}{(1-\theta)bc} (e^{bT}-e^{bt_2}) \right| \tag{22}$$

from eq(17), (21) and (22), we see that t_1, t_2, t_3 are mutually dependent among them one act as decision variable. t_1 is decision variable.

Now taking equation (8)

$$I'_r(t) = -q_1P \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1$$

Integrating w.r.t. t

$$I_r(t) = \int_0^t -q_1P dt$$

$$= -q_1Pt \tag{23}$$

(i) The present worth of holding cost for used and imperfect items is

$$HC_R = h_R \left[\int_0^{t_1} I_{u_i}(t)e^{-rt} dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} I_{u_i}(t)e^{-rt} dt + \int_{t_2}^{t_3} I_{u_i}(t)e^{-rt} dt \right]$$

$$= h_R \left[\frac{\varphi a}{b} \left\{ \frac{e^{(b-r)t_1}-1}{b-r} + \frac{e^{-rt_1}-1}{r} \right\} + \theta P \left(\frac{t_1 e^{-rt_1}}{-r} - \frac{e^{-rt_1}-1}{r^2} \right) + \frac{\varphi a}{b} \left\{ \frac{e^{(b-r)t_2}-e^{(b-r)t_1}}{b-r} + \frac{(e^{-rt_2}-e^{-rt_1})}{r} \right\} + \frac{k\theta a(e^{bt_1-1})(e^{-rt_2}-e^{-rt_1})}{-br} + \frac{\varphi a}{b} \left\{ \frac{e^{(b-r)t_3}-e^{(b-r)t_2}}{b-r} + \frac{e^{bt_3}(e^{-rt_3}-e^{-rt_2})}{r} \right\} + \frac{(1-\theta)c}{d} \left\{ \frac{e^{(d-r)t_3}-e^{(d-r)t_2}}{d-r} + \frac{e^{dt_3}(e^{-rt_3}-e^{-rt_2})}{r} \right\} \right] \tag{24}$$

(ii) The present worth of holding cost for finished items is

$$HC_P = h_P \left[\int_0^{t_1} I_f(t)e^{-rt} dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} I_f(t)e^{-rt} dt + \int_{t_2}^{t_3} I_f(t)e^{-rt} dt \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= h_p \left[\frac{-a}{b} \left\{ \frac{e^{(b-r)t_1} - 1}{b-r} + \frac{e^{-rt_1} - 1}{r} \right\} + (1-\theta)P \left(\frac{t_1 e^{-rt_1}}{-r} - \frac{e^{-rt_1} - 1}{r^2} \right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{-a}{b} \left\{ \frac{e^{(b-r)t_2} - e^{(b-r)t_1}}{b-r} + \frac{e^{bt_2}(e^{-rt_2} - e^{-rt_1})}{r} \right\} - \frac{a}{b} \left\{ \frac{e^{(b-r)t_3} - e^{(b-r)t_2}}{b-r} + \frac{e^{bt_3}(e^{-rt_3} - e^{-rt_2})}{r} \right\} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{(1-\theta)c}{d} \left\{ \frac{e^{(d-r)t_3} - e^{(d-r)t_2}}{d-r} + \frac{e^{dt_3}(e^{-rt_3} - e^{-rt_2})}{r} \right\} \right] \tag{25}
 \end{aligned}$$

(iii) The present worth of holding cost for Raw Material is

$$\begin{aligned}
 HC_1 &= h_1 \left[\int_0^{t_1} I_r(t) e^{-rt} dt \right] \\
 &= h_1 \left[\frac{qka}{b} \left[\frac{e^{(b-r)t_1} - 1}{b-r} - \frac{e^{bt_1}(e^{-rt_1} - 1)}{-r} \right] \right] \\
 &\quad \dots\dots\dots eq(26)
 \end{aligned}$$

(iv) The present worth of production cost is

$$\begin{aligned}
 PC &= c_2 \left[\int_0^{t_1} kae^{bt} e^{-rt} dt \right] \\
 &= c_2 \left[\frac{ka(e^{(b-r)t_1} - 1)}{b-r} \right] \dots\dots\dots eq(27)
 \end{aligned}$$

(v) The present worth of returned items cost is

$$\begin{aligned}
 AC &= u_R \left[\int_0^{t_3} \psi D(t) e^{-rt} dt \right] \\
 &= u_R \left[\frac{\psi a(e^{(b-r)t_3} - 1)}{b-r} \right] \dots\dots\dots eq(28)
 \end{aligned}$$

(vi) The present worth of remanufacturing cost is

$$\begin{aligned}
 RC &= i \left[\int_{t_2}^{t_3} ce^{dt} e^{-rt} dt \right] \\
 &= i \left[\frac{c(e^{(d-r)t_3} - e^{(d-r)t_2})}{d-r} \right] \dots\dots\dots eq(29)
 \end{aligned}$$

(vii) The present worth of inspection cost is

$$\begin{aligned}
 IC &= l \left[\int_0^{t_1} Pe^{-rt} dt + \int_{t_2}^{t_3} R(t) e^{-rt} dt \right] \\
 &= l \left[P \left(\frac{e^{-rt_1} - 1}{-r} \right) + c \left(\frac{e^{(d-r)t_3} - e^{(d-r)t_2}}{d-r} \right) \right] \tag{30}
 \end{aligned}$$

MODEL FOR TRADE CREDIT ON USED AND IMPERFECT ITEMS:

$$\begin{aligned}
 IE &= Ec_3 \left[\int_0^{t_1} (t_1 - t) I_{u_i}(t) dt + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (t_2 - t) I_{u_i}(t) dt + \int_{t_2}^{t_3} (t_3 - t) I_{u_i}(t) dt \right] \\
 &= Ec_3 \left[\left\{ \frac{(\varphi + \theta k)a}{b} \left[\frac{-t_1}{b} + \frac{e^{bt_1}}{b^2} - \frac{1}{b^2} - \frac{t^2}{2} \right] + \left[\frac{e^{bt_2}}{b^2} - \frac{t_2^2}{2} - \frac{e^{bt_1}(t_2 - t_1)}{b} - \frac{e^{bt_1}}{b^2} + t_2 t_1 - \frac{t_1^2}{2} \right] \right\} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \left\{ \frac{\varphi a}{b} \left[\frac{e^{bt_3}}{b^2} - \frac{t_3^2}{2} - e^{bt_2} \left(\frac{t_3^2}{2} \right) - \frac{e^{bt_2}(t_3 - t_2)}{b} - \frac{e^{bt_2}}{b^2} + t_3 t_2 - \frac{t_2^2}{2} + e^{bt_2} \left(t_3 - \frac{t_2}{2} \right) \right] \right\} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \left\{ \frac{(1-\theta)c}{d} \left[\frac{e^{dt_3}}{d^2} - \frac{t_3^2}{2} - e^{dt_2} \left(\frac{t_3^2}{2} \right) - \frac{e^{dt_2}(t_3 - t_2)}{d} - \frac{e^{dt_2}}{d^2} + t_3 t_2 - \frac{t_2^2}{2} + e^{dt_2} \left(t_3 - \frac{t_2}{2} \right) \right] \right\} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

when $0 \leq M \leq t_1$, here use the trade credit from M to t_3

$$IP_1 = Rc_3 \left[\int_M^{t_3} I_{u_i}(t) dt \right]$$

$$= Rc_3 \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\varphi a}{b} \left[\frac{e^{bt_2}}{b} - t_2 - \frac{e^{bM}}{b} + M \right] \\ + \frac{k\theta a}{b} \left[t_2 e^{bt_1} - t_2 - Me^{bt_1} + M \right] \\ + \frac{\varphi a}{b} \left[\frac{e^{bt_3}}{b} - t_3 e^{bt_3} - \frac{e^{bt_2}}{b} + t_2 e^{bt_3} \right] \\ - \frac{(1-\theta)c}{d} \left[\frac{e^{dt_3}}{d} - t_3 e^{dt_3} - \frac{e^{dt_2}}{b} + t_2 e^{dt_3} \right] \end{array} \right\}$$

Optimality condition:

total cost = $C_R + C_P + C_1 + HC_R + HC_P + HC + PC + AC + RC + IC + IP_1 - IE$

Total cost Per unit time $TC^*(X, T) = \text{total cost} / T = X^* / T$

where $X^* = C_R + C_P + C_1 + HC_R + HC_P + HC + PC + AC + RC + IC + IP_1 - IE$

$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_1}(TC^*(X^*, T)) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial T}(TC^*(X^*, T)) = 0$

$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_1^2}(TC^*(X^*, T)) > 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2}{\partial T^2}(TC^*(X^*, T)) > 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t_1 \partial T}(TC^*(X^*, T)) < 0$

6. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

This section is used to solve a numerical example with the aim to illustrate and validate the proposed inventory model. For this MATLAB is used to obtain the optimal solution of the objective solution in consideration.

Where $a = 250, b = 0.2, c = 500, d = 0.1, CP = 100, CR = 150, C1 = 50, hP = 2, hR = 0.5, h1 = 1, c2 = 10, uR = 2, l = 2, i = 10, k = 25, \varphi = 0.5, \delta = 0.1, r = 0.04, q1 = 1, c3 = 100, M = .003, E = 0.12, R = 0.15, t2 = 0.1$
 then we find $t_1 = 0.001, T = 0.4923, TAC = 27270.95662$

7. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Sensitivity analysis with respect to some input parameters of the inventory model is shown in Table For the different parameters, different levels are chosen as follows: -20%, -10%, 10% and 20% respectively.

8. OBSERVATION:

From the table we observe that with increases the demand parameter ‘a’, the cycle time T decreases and total cost (TC*) increases, with increases the demand parameter ‘b’, the cycle time T increases and total cost (TC*) decreases, with increases the permissible delay in payment (M), total cost (TC*) increases and with increases the purchasing cost (c3) total cost also increase

Parameter	Change in parameter	t ₁	T	TC*
A	-20%	0.0001	0.585755764	23570.57393

	-10%	0.000 1	0.534055 410	25495.73 182
	10%	0.000 1	0.457887 544	28904.91 1
	20%	0.000 1	0.429022 770	30405.69 525
b	-20%	0.000 115	0.416998 362	31106.34 246
	-10%	0.000 107	0.454972 528	29064.53 022
	10%	0.000 092	0.528933 420	25694.32 363
	20%	0.000 085	0.564791 404	24306.78 239
M	-20%	0.000 1	0.492306 44	27270.96 393
	-10%	0.000 1	0.492306 44	27290.30 595
	10%	0.000 1	0.492306 44	27309.63 997
	20%	0.000 1	0.492306 44	27328.96 946
c₃	-20%	0.000 1	0.492306 44	26348.00 77
	-10%	0.000 1	0.492306 44	26860.43 026
	10%	0.000 1	0.492306 44	27605.94 901
	20%	0.000 1	0.492306 44	27885.60 265

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